
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION AS TOOLS FOR ACQUISITION OF INNOVATIVE AND ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS FOR POVERTY ERADICATION TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This paper discussed the relevance of science and technology education, as important instruments for acquiring innovative and entrepreneurial skills for poverty eradication towards sustainable development in Nigeria. Specifically, this paper explained some of the best and easiest ways of eradicating poverty in order to achieve sustainable development as to be through acquisition of innovative and entrepreneurial skills embedded in the science and technology curriculum from secondary and tertiary levels of education. Innovative and entrepreneurial skills acquisition in Nigeria entails focusing on what should be done to bridge the gap between the school and labour market, where the learner will work after graduation, so as to be self-sustain and self-reliant in the society and also to guarantee sustainable development. Entrepreneurship is considered as an alternative way to tackle some of the socio-economic problems that bedevilled many nations presently and Nigeria is not an exceptional, especially the problem of high rate of poverty due to the high rate of unemployment in Nigeria. Innovative and entrepreneurial skills are acquired through training that emphasizes the acquisition and development of appropriate knowledge and skills and enable an individual to maximize the resources around him within the limit of his capability which could invariably lead to poverty eradication and thereby resulting to sustainable development. It was concluded that science and technology education must be given due attention by the ministry of education and the teachers in secondary and tertiary institutions as it could equip learners with the appropriate innovative and entrepreneurial skills for poverty eradication; stimulating employment and economic growth and thereby resulting to sustainable development. The paper recommended among others that, since innovative and entrepreneurial skills can be acquired through efficient and effective knowledge of science and technology; science and technology education should be taught with relevant and appropriate tools by teachers.

Keywords: Science and technology education, innovative and entrepreneurial skills, poverty eradication, sustainable development.

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Introduction

Innovative and entrepreneurial skill acquisition and other means of eradicating poverty are key issues that have been receiving attention globally. Training the learners to acquire useful skills helps them to live a fulfilled life after graduation. Education is an instrument for sustainable development and social change of any nation, Nigeria is not an exceptional. In the National Policy on Education (FGN, 2014), it was clearly stated that education maximizes the creative potentials and skills of the individual for self-fulfilment and general development of the society. Education is regarded as the greatest mass rewarding and ending investment in human capital. It is a means of acquiring experience, knowledge and skills aimed at eliminating the shackles of ignorance thereby enhancing one's development as well as the development of one's community (Igwe, 2014). Science and technology education teaching in general aims at equipped the learners with appropriate scientific and innovative knowledge and skills which will enable them to explore their surroundings and become more creative and self-reliant (Ajayi & Angura, 2017). The knowledge and skills which students acquire could be of value by helping them develop entrepreneurial skills for job creation, thereby leading to poverty eradication. Okoli and Onwuachu (2019), posited that exposing students to scientific and innovative skills through practical lessons could enable them acquire skills to develop the capacity for critical thinking, generate ideas; and be able to repair and/or service simple electrical connections and wirings in the home, service and maintain mobile phones, electricity generating sets, radios, and other household electronics.

One of the problems facing Nigeria and many other developing nations has been that of poverty due to unemployment. Majority of college, polytechnic and university graduates are unemployed. Given the prevailing unemployment situation in Nigeria among university graduates, which currently stands at around 55% (Salami, 2011), entrepreneurial education in the university has become crucial to enable graduates create job instead of job seekers. This perhaps may be because of over dependence on government jobs or white-collar jobs. In the country today, graduates cannot create jobs; they strive to be employees of labour rather than being employers in their various fields. Nevertheless, these problems could lead to crimes such as youth restiveness, prostitution, armed robbery, drug abuse and kidnapping amongst others. These vices could be detrimental to investment promotion, economic growth and consequently have a negative feedback effect on employment. Ajayi (2019) concluded that the absence of sustainable economic growth and job creation, which are considered very instrumental in poverty eradication are the pressing challenges facing Nigeria today. The problem keeps crying for solutions and government feels that something must be done to get out of the waterloo and so one of the measures put in place by the federal government of Nigeria is to mandate schools from secondary to tertiary level of education to include the teaching of innovative and entrepreneurship skills in their curriculum.

Innovative and entrepreneurship skills are one of the instruments for achieving sustainable development as well as employment creation and thereby eradicating poverty. Innovative and entrepreneurship skills allow youths to seek for success in ventures through one's effort. Innovative and entrepreneurs' skills transform youths to be responsible and enterprising individuals, who become entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial thinkers by exposing them to real life learning experiences. Entrepreneurs are innovators who are capable of developing new technologies, new product and service adapting existing technologies to new use. According to Inegbenebor (2006), entrepreneurship skills raise the level of productivity in the economy by harnessing and utilizing resources efficiently. Entrepreneurship is the backbone of every vibrant and resilient economy. The importance of entrepreneurship in enhancing human capital development in terms of poverty eradication, employment generation, wealth creation and economic vitality has given entrepreneurship worldwide recognition. Learners should be equipped with appropriate scientific, technological knowledge and skills that will empower them economically for survival in our modern age of science and technology. The best and easiest way of achieving this is through acquisition of innovative and entrepreneurial skills embedded in the science and technology curriculum for the secondary and tertiary levels of education. Thus, the need for the pursuit of poverty eradication through innovative and entrepreneurship skills acquire through science and technology education is highly essential for growth and structural transformation of an economy and the attainment of sustainable development.

Science Education

Science is a branch of study that is concerned with facts, principles and methods. It is the knowledge acquired by careful observation and deduction of the laws which govern changes and conditions by testing those deductions by experiments. Science education is the field concerned with sharing science content and process with individuals not traditionally considered part of the scientific community (Agbowuro, Oriade, Shuaibu, 2015). Science education teaching in general aims at equipped the learners with appropriate scientific knowledge and skills which will enable them to explore their surroundings and become more creative and self-reliant.

Science is a process as well as knowledge. Children learn science by being involved not only with its content, but also with its methodology. The field of science education includes work in science content, science process (the scientific method) and teaching pedagogy. Science process skills are mental and physical abilities and competences which serve as tools needed for effective study of science and technology as well as problem solving for individuals and societal development (Nwosu & Nwaocha, 2014). The knowledge of science education prepares students to be actively engaged and responsible citizens, creative and innovative, able to work collaboratively and fully aware of and conversant with the complex challenges facing society (European Commission, 2015).

The knowledge of science also helps in explaining and understanding the world around us. Science education is very important in promoting a culture of scientific thinking and inspiring citizens to use evidence-based reasoning for decision making; ensuring citizens have the confidence, knowledge and skills to participate actively in an increasingly complex scientific and technological world; developing the competencies for problem-solving and innovation, as well as analytical and critical thinking that are necessary to empower citizens to lead personally fulfilling, socially responsible and professionally-engaged lives and inspiring children and students of all ages and talents to aspire to careers in science and other occupations and professions that underpin our knowledge and innovation-intensive societies (Ajayi, Achor, Otor, 2019). Thus, the knowledge and skills which science students acquire could be of value by helping them develop entrepreneurial skills for job creation and thereby leading to poverty eradication. In other words, the development of science process skills should lead to acquisition of the entrepreneurial skills that successful entrepreneurs use to start their ventures. Science process skill is the interface between transfer of knowledge and entrepreneurial skill which is necessary for problem solving and functional living.

Technology Education

Technology education is the only subject area specifically designed to deliver technological literacy. Technology education involves the study and practice of the theory, principles and processes by which technology may be used to facilitate/support learning and improve performance. The International Test and Evaluation Association (2000) defined technology education as the study of technology in which students learn about the process and knowledge related to technology. As a field of study, it covers the human ability to shape and change the physical world to meet needs, by manipulating materials and tools with techniques. As a concept, it is concerning an array of tools such as media, machines and networking hardware, as well as considering underlining theoretical perspectives for their effective application (Richey, 2000). It is a means of preparing for occupational field and for effective participation in the world of work, an aspect of lifelong learning a preparation for responsible citizenship and an instrument for promoting environmentally sound sustainable development. It provides trained manpower in the applied sciences and technology. It proffers the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for sustainable development.

Innovative and Entrepreneurial Skills

Skills are described as the ability to apply knowledge in practice, a special ability that drives innovation and development. Skill is a testable ability of performing a task. In entrepreneurship, highly developed science and technology skills can help student or graduate entrepreneurs accurately identify and acquire effective resources in a dynamic and complex social environment, as well as create a new combination of technology and knowledge with the support of organizations.

Skill is a well-established habit of doing something. Skill acquisition is a process where the youths through learning of necessary skills that will enable them to be self-reliance becomes useful to the society by embarking on profitable entrepreneurship programme (Ajayi, 2019). Aniodoh (2011) described skill acquisition as the ability to perform a task either mental or manual, which involves working out or building up series of process and actions into a consolidated progression.

Innovative skill is generally regarded as the product or application of creativity. Innovativeness is the ability of introducing or using new ideas or ways of doing things. In other words, innovation skill is the ability to apply new ideas that enable one to approach activities differently in order to achieve better results it is all about improving on the existing way of doing things through personal initiatives, imagination and insight. The process of innovation involves thinking creatively; using imagination to manipulate instruments or variables, to formulate models, to discover possibilities, and to construct objects and images that never existed before. Innovation can be a change made in established laws and practices by the introduction of something new, with the purpose of improving quality, quantity, output, or procedures. Innovative skill is seen as an internal driver skill; innovation relates to an entrepreneurial mindset; thus, development of new products or entrance to new markets is the result of entrepreneurship (Miller, 2013). The innovative skilled person is able to change things around or devise new ways of doing things in order to accommodate whatever new situation that may arise. Thus, innovativeness can thus be seen as the specific instrument of entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurial skill consists of effective utilization of ideas, information and facts that help a learner develop competencies, services needed for firm career commitments such as setting up business, marketing, services or being productive, wealth creators, employers of labour and self-reliant thereby contributing in nation building. An entrepreneurial skill according to Olagunju (2016) is the ability of an individual to exploit an idea and create an enterprise whether big or small not only for personal gain but also for social and developmental gain. Entrepreneurial skills are the ability to have self-belief, boldness, tenacity, passionate, empathy, readiness to take expert advice, desire for immediate result, visionary and ability to recognize opportunity. Hisrich and Peters (2017) defined entrepreneurial skill as the ability to create something new with value by devoting the necessary time and effort, assuming the resulting rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction and independence. Entrepreneurial skills are acquired through training that emphasizes the acquisition and development of appropriate knowledge and skill that will enable an individual to maximize the resources around him within the limit of his capability.

Entrepreneurial skills are business skills, which an individual acquires personally to function effectively in business as an entrepreneur and be self-reliant (Umunadi, 2014).

Entrepreneurship has to do with a system of ideas and values that are not ordinarily treated as part of the curriculum, it is the process of using private initiative to transform a business concept into a new venture or to grow and diversify an existing venture or enterprise with high growth potential (Ugwoke & Abidde, 2014). Therefore, entrepreneurship could be seen as the act of identifying, initiating, organizing, and bringing an idea or vision to life, be it a new product, service, process, strategy, or market. It is all about self-employment, which is very important for improving an individual's quality of life and national development. Consequently, entrepreneurship education leads to the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills for efficient and effective living; it gives the youths more opportunities to exercise creative freedom, higher self-esteem, and a greater sense of control over their own lives. An entrepreneur is one who undertakes the risk of organizing and managing a business. The entrepreneur looks inward into his/her environment to identify problems confronting people (or business opportunities) and introduces new products and services for the purpose of making profit. Moemeke (2013) stated that an entrepreneur is, therefore, not only an innovator but also a lifelong learner, a creative person, an initiator, and a potential industrialist. By implication, entrepreneurs are innovators who are capable of developing new technologies, new product and service adapting existing technologies to new use. Thus, the destiny of nations lies with the entrepreneurs since they shape, actualize, and bring the developmental dreams and economy of any nation to reality.

The Need for Innovative and Entrepreneurial Skills

The inability of the graduates of the educational system to contribute meaningfully to the economic development of the nation by being self-employed was what informed the need to inculcate entrepreneurship into schools' subject's curriculum. The call for the introduction of entrepreneurship in schools is an indication of its importance in economic empowerment and job creation for sustainable development in particular. Innovative and entrepreneur skills have become necessary as Nigeria continues to churn out graduates that are hardly self-reliant but solely dependent on white collar job. Innovative and entrepreneurial skills are forms of knowledge that seeks to prepare people specially to be responsible and enterprising individuals who become entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial thinkers to contribute to economic and sustainable communities. Cherwitz (2016) viewed entrepreneurial skills as the ability to educate people who will utilize their intellectual prowess to add to disciplinary knowledge as a lever for social and economic good. Okoli (2011) identified the benefits of innovative and entrepreneurs' skills to include the following. It will help the students after graduation to:

- i. Become entrepreneurial thinkers who also have the skills and tools to start their own business.
- ii. Demonstrate skills in maintaining business longevity.
- iii. Access other resources and services.

- iv. Demonstrate innovative/operation skills.
- v. Change personal and career attitudes including: ability to control one's own life, personality, creativity and interpersonal communications.

Science and Technology Education as Tools for Acquisition of Innovative and Entrepreneurial Skills

Science and technology education are responsible for equipping individuals with requisite skills, creativity and innovativeness needed to become entrepreneurs. It is also tools for innovative and entrepreneurial skills that pave way for the building of good human and personal relations needed to address personal and social challenges such as poverty (Ajayi & Ogbeba, 2017). By implication, science and technology education provides the necessary innovative and entrepreneurial skills to learners which help reduce the number of people who are unemployed after graduation by providing them the opportunity to be self-employed in order to escape poverty. The knowledge in science and technology education can lead to acquisition of innovative skills in various forms such as product innovations, improvisation innovative; process (including marketing process) innovations; organization and management innovations; and technology innovations. In the same vein, the following are some of the entrepreneur skills science subjects could provide for learners:

In introductory technology, woodwork, glass work (glass ornament, glass blowing, production of glass wares), welding, smiting (black, iron, gold, and brass), ceramics, metal and electrical works, shoe-making and repairs and host of others entrepreneurial skills can be acquired by the students if they are effective taught.

In biological/agricultural sciences, animal husbandry skills which include: functional fishery, bee-keeping, snail farming, rabbit farming, poultry, piggery. Horticulture skills which include raising vegetable gardens and mushroom farming, arable farming and floriculture, also biotechnology which involves animals and plants breeding to improve varieties.

In physical sciences, various skills such as, extraction of dyes and indicators from plant parts, production of tie and dye cloth, soap making, perfume production, polish making, wine brewing production of bottled and distilled waters, pesticides, pomade making, vegetable oil, battery charging, vulcanizing, repairs of some simple electrical appliances like pressing iron, handsets, fans and generators can also be acquired.

The impact of technology education in the acquisition of innovative and entrepreneurial skills cannot be overemphasized. The knowledge of technology education helps us connected with the world around us and acts as a portal to vast amounts of knowledge which can be accessed with ease. The following are some of the innovative and entrepreneur skills technology provide:

Communication: Good communication is necessary to allow efficient flow of information in a business. Technology education provides multiple channels for businesses to communicate both internally and externally.

The knowledge of technology education can be used as an outlet which allows businesses to collect feedback from their customers, which can be used to improve a product to suit the needs of the customers better.

Web based product advertising: One of the most beneficial uses of the knowledge of technology education is advertising to millions of people around the globe. Web based advertising consists of websites and social media.

Research and development: Through the use of technology, businesses can research the market through the use of secondary data. This is extremely useful as it provides businesses with in-depth knowledge about markets before penetrating them. Along with secondary research, businesses can use technology education to conduct primary research in addition to using online surveys and customer feedback.

Based on the assertions above, it is obvious that innovative and entrepreneur skills involves the acquisition and utilization of skills for innovativeness, creativity and productivity via science and technology education so as to be economically self-reliant and for national sustainable development.

Poverty Eradication for Sustainable Development

Poverty eradication is top priority of the United Nations nineteen (19) objectives for achieving Sustainable Development in developing economy (UNESCO, 2015). According to World Bank (2011), “poverty is the economic condition in which people lack sufficient income to obtain certain minimal levels of health services, food, housing, clothing and education which are necessities for standard of living”. Poverty in the face of abundance is now the world’s greatest challenge and major developmental objective is the achievement of equality in the distribution of income and reduction of poverty. Poverty may be defined as lack of basic things of life, such as food, clothing, shelter and access to portable water, all of which determine the quality of our life. It may also include access to opportunities such as education and employment which aid the escape from poverty and/or allow one to enjoy the respect of fellow citizens. Poverty in general, entails a state in which an individual or household is unable to meet the basic needs of life considered as minimum requirements, to sustain livelihood in the given society (Ajayi, Aboho & Ajayi, 2018). Poverty is an unacceptable deprivation in human well-being that can comprise both physiological and social deprivation.

According to Nweze and Ojowu (2012), poverty can be subdivided into three namely: absolute poverty, relative poverty and subjective poverty. One of the major challenges facing developing and underdeveloped countries of the world is poverty. It has been so endemic as a result of the high rate of unemployment that has become the major characteristic of the developing and underdeveloped countries of the world (Adofu and Ocheja 2013). In Nigeria, poverty still remains the major obstacle to the success of the struggle for the optimum utilization of human resources for both social and economic development of nations.

Collier (2017) concluded that more than a billion people, live in extreme poverty in spite of the Nigeria's vast resources, the country is known for her low Gross Domestic Product (GDP), low per capital income, high unemployment rate, low industrial utilization capacity and high birth rate.

Entrepreneurship is globally recognized as a strategic mechanism or the driving force of sustainable economic growth, through innovation, creativity and job creation as well as its welfare effects on poverty incidence across international boundaries (Herrington and Kew 2014). A good number of academic studies have shown that entrepreneurial endeavours' have the capability of pulling people out of poverty, whether they start their own business or being employed by another entrepreneur (Silvinski 2012). He further explained that the consistent experience of being self-employed is the most effective strategy for economic mobility. However, an increased rate of entrepreneurship in a nation translates to drastic declines in the rate of poverty. Kareem (2015) believes that entrepreneurship takes the centre stage in promoting prosperity by creating new jobs, reducing poverty as well as increasing economic growth of a nation. Entrepreneurship boosts productivity by introducing new innovations and fast-tracking structural changes thereby forcing existing businesses to reform and increase competition.

According to Agwuogu (2013), sustainable development is the type of development that can be initiated and managed properly in such a way as to give attention to continuity and preservation as people explore available resources for the enlargement of their existence. In essence, sustainable development is a process of change in which the exploitation of resources, the direction of investments, the orientation of technological development and institutional change are all in harmony and enhance both current and future potential to meet human needs and aspirations.

Sustainable development entails that resources that are renewable should be employed in every possible situation and resources that are non-renewable should be used rarely in order to ensure their viability for the future generations to come (Patil, 2014). Sustainable development entails the designing of a social and economic system that ensures that standards of education continues to improve, the rise in the real income is maintained, the economic growth of the nation continues to improve as well as other aspect of life continues to increase (Kyro, 2015). This cannot occur if the right type of education is not given to individuals. Sustainable development can be viewed in three dimensions namely; Economic, environmental and social (United Nations, 2005). The goals of sustainable development include: End of poverty in all its forms across boards; Establish infrastructures while promoting inclusive and sustainable commercialization while fostering innovations; Ensure healthy lives and promotion of well-being for all; Guaranty equal and inclusive education while promoting long-lasting learning opportunities for all; Ensuring gender equity and empowerment of females;

Guarantee available and sustainable management of water and sanitation for everyone; Available employment for everyone across boards; Mitigate the inequality within and among nations; Ensure that cities and settlement are safety, conscious, inclusive and sustainable; Guarantee sustainable consumption and production patterns; Embark on actions that tackle climate change its implications; Preserve and sustainable employ oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development; and provision of access to justice while building accountable and inclusive institutions at all level of governance.

From these goals mentioned above it can be deduced that the objective of sustainable development is focused on reconciling the issues of economic development that is necessary for higher standard of living with that of enhancing with the challenges being faced in Nigeria. Both scholars and policymakers have proposed that acquisition of innovative and entrepreneurial skills is an effective means for economic development and poverty eradication in impoverished and lower income regions of the world (Mead and Liedholm, 2018). In the face of the global issues that result to high rate of poverty, the science and technology education could be used as tool to acquire innovative and entrepreneurial skills to eradicate poverty toward sustainable development.

Issues Affecting Innovative and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition via Science and Technology Education

- i. Mode of Instructional delivery: Instructional delivery mode has been based on rote learning, memorisation of facts and reproduction of the same at examinations. The method used has largely been over 70% class teaching with library assignments and laboratory work making the other 10 - 30% (Ajayi, 2019). Conventional assessment of rote-learned information using closed book examinations is the norm. Very little or no interaction with laboratory or field and ICT centre takes place to enrich the learning programme.
- ii. Inadequate facilities: The laboratories and other facilities are not adequate and functional which retard learning. Irregular water and light supply which increase frustration during practical. Most equipment in the laboratories is out-dated and is not usually replaced.
- iii. Lack of awareness on the importance of science and knowledge: Inadequate funding: Funding of secondary and tertiary institutions in Nigeria has remained a very difficult issue for both government and the administrators. Tertiary education is very cost intensive in terms of both capital and recurrent expenditures. Most often different staff unions of the tertiary institutions embark on strike because of non-payment of adequate remuneration.

Conclusion

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Since innovative and entrepreneurial skills can be acquired through efficient and effective knowledge of science and technology; science and technology education should be taught with relevant and appropriate tools by teachers.

- ii. Government should adequately fund science and technology education, so as to train and retrain professionals and qualified teachers for functional science and technology education; and to set-up entrepreneurial science and technology training centre that could be used for practical purposes.
- iii. Only qualified and competent teachers should be employed to teach science and technology in schools in order to impact the appropriate science and technology skills needed to be a successful entrepreneur.
- iv. There should be awareness campaign to sensitize the citizenry on the benefits of science and technology education.

Recommendations

The acquisition of appropriate skills and the development of mental, physical, social, innovative and entrepreneurial abilities/competencies were necessary for the individual to live in, survive poverty and contribute to the development of the society. One of the consequences of unemployment is poverty. Eradicating poverty in all its forms and dimensions, including extreme poverty, is the greatest global challenge and an indispensable requirement for sustainable development. The first Sustainable Development Goal aims to “End poverty in all its forms everywhere”. Its seven associated targets aims, among others, to eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, reduce at least by half the proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty. To totally address the issue of unemployment and eradicate poverty in Nigeria, there is a great need for the acquisition of innovative and entrepreneurial skills for employable individuals. These innovative and entrepreneurial skills can be efficiently and effectively acquired with the knowledge of science and technology education.

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